

NDAC/LO/129
Dec 7, 1989

30th NDAC Report from Lund Observatory

WP6000: Step 2/3 (Lindegren)

A tape with the great-circle reductions of 23 sets (perfect catalogue and perfect attitude), with corresponding star coordinates and attitude files, has been received from CUO. The corresponding interface modules for Step 2/3 (PREP23 and SORT23) have been modified according to the specifications in GCIS-4 and GCOS-2. The files were read and interpreted without any problems, and the sorting of the abscissae was also performed as expected. Further analysis will be made in December.

WP8000: Double Stars (Söderhjelm)

A set of double star simulations with the recovery orbit (and 'ideal' 3-station coverage) were made for different mission durations. As reported in C , the results were encouraging, with useful results after about 18 months of observations. Work is proceeding on the preparatory programs needed for the CHF-generation. This includes a detailed look on the actual double and multiple star data in the Input Catalogue.

Miscellaneous (Lindegren)

A simulation of sky coverage and astrometric precision for the revised mission was made in early September (C). Other simulations performed during this period include OTF calculations for various wavefront errors, indicating that a certain twisting of the beam combiner may be the most likely explanation of the 21 mas phase difference observed between the first and second harmonics of the real IDT data.

Working papers:

- C = NDAC/LO/127 (Lindegren, 1989 Sept 7):
Sky Coverage and Astrometric Precision for a Recovery Mission
- C = NDAC/LO/128 (Söderhjelm, 1989 Oct 5):
HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, XI